

GENDER-DEPENDENT CHARACTERISTICS OF VEGETATIVE CHANGES DURING TRIGEMINAL NEURALGIA ATTACKS

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Significance: trigeminal neuralgia stands as one of the prevalent and enduring pain syndromes encountered in clinical neurology. Epidemiological investigations conducted in the United States have delineated an incidence rate averaging 4.3-4.7 cases per 100,000 individuals within the populace. Regarding prevalence, trigeminal neuralgia occupies the second position following facial neuropathy among the spectrum of cranial nerve disorders. While the affliction predominantly manifests in individuals of middle to advanced age, a notable proportion, constituting 30-35%, experiences inaugural symptomatic episodes prior to reaching the age of 40. Additionally, initial onset of trigeminal neuralgia in individuals aged over 70 years comprises approximately 2-3% of cases. Noteworthy gender disparity is observed, with a higher predilection noted among females compared to males. Notably, trigeminal neuralgia episodes are concomitant with a myriad of autonomic and vascular changes. This phenomenon may be explicated through the response elicited by the sympathetic-parasympathetic apparatus, given the robust connectivity between the trigeminal nerve and the autonomic nervous system.

Research aim: the objective of this investigation is to conduct a gender-stratified examination of autonomic fluctuations during painful episodes of trigeminal neuralgia. By elucidating gender-specific autonomic responses, this study endeavors to contribute to a nuanced comprehension of trigeminal neuralgia pathophysiology, thereby facilitating the development of tailored therapeutic interventions.

Materials and Methods: This study comprised a clinical investigation involving 238 participants aged between 30 and 70 years, receiving care at the departments of neurology and maxillofacial surgery within the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center. The cohort included 155 females and 83 males. All subjects underwent autonomic assessments to ascertain the presence of autonomic dystonia syndrome.

Results and Discussion: Autonomic evaluations were conducted on a subset of patients, yielding the following findings. Regarding the assessment of coldness and numbness via vegetative testing, coldness observed in the fingertips and palms was documented in 18% of females and 13.2% of males, while coldness and numbness encompassing all areas of the fingers were

reported in 15% of females and 8% of males. Examination of color changes in the fingertips and palms (e.g., pallor, redness) revealed a color alteration prevalence of 25.8% among females and 12% among males. Notably, uniform discoloration of the entire finger and palm occurred in nearly equivalent proportions across genders.

Utilizing a vegetative test, we identified a notable gender discrepancy in perspiration levels during pain episodes, with a higher incidence observed among women (32%) compared to men (29%).

Trigeminal neuralgia episodes are marked by a plethora of autonomic vascular alterations. When scrutinizing heart rate variations during painful episodes utilizing vegetative testing, instances of tachycardia or bradycardia were detected in 74% of females and 62.6% of males.

In conclusion, the examination outcomes delineate a consistent pattern of facial erythema, pallor, indications of coldness and numbness upon stimulation, alterations in fingertip and palm coloration (e.g., pallor, erythema), perspiration during pain episodes, and fluctuations in heart rate, with a higher prevalence noted among women compared to men. These findings underscore the heightened occurrence of vegetative dystonia syndrome among women (86.5%) during painful episodes.

References:

1. Гречко В.ЕК диагностике невралгий тройничного нерва//Журн. невропат.и психиатр. 1985; 7: 1053-1055.
2. Грачев Ю.В., Климов Б.А., Молодецких В.А. и др. Лицевые боли как проявление психических расстройств. //Ж. неврологии и психиатрии. 2002. - №4. - С. 13-16.
3. .А.В. Степанченко. Типичная невралгия тройничного нерва.// М., Изд. группа "ВХМ",1994, 39с.
4. Юдельсон Я.Б., Грибова Н.П. Лицевые гиперкинезы и дистонии. Смоленск 1997, 36-44Unger RK. Towards a redefinition of sex and gender. AmPsychol 1979; 34:1085-1094
5. Myers CD, Wise EA, Riley JL. Relative contributions of sex and gender to cardiovascular reactivity and experimental pain response. Poster. 17th annual meeting of the American Pain 14.
6. Жураева, Д. Н., & Нарзулаева, У. Р. (2020). Эркак ва аёлларда уч шошли нерв невралгияси кечишининг параклиник хусусиятлари. ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ, 1(1).Society, San Diego, California, November 1998;